

ISic3479

Sikel inscription on wall of a tomb

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

rock face

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Palagonia

Provenance

Tomb 15 was identified in 1990 at the Coste di S. Febronia, near Palagonia

Coordinates

37.32519, 14.76745

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palagonia, in situ

Physical Description

A rock-cut tomb (Tomb 15) in the Coste di S. Frebonia, consisting of an entry and single chamber, with inscriptions on two walls, of which this is the right hand wall

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

The text is laid out on the right hand wall (as one enters) of the roughly rectangular chamber. Two sequences of letters run in the upper line from left to right and in the lower line from right to left, with a final letter below.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 60-85 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. BAΨIAE

2. BAPIΓA

3. M

Apparatus

Text of Cordano

Cordano suggests it is possible to read K instead of IF

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645100

EDCS 70901062

PHI 336138

PHI 337256

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3479. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358568>